

Low-velocity impact response of sandwich plates with a metal foam core

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Abstract: An analytical model is developed to predict the dynamic response of fully clamped square sandwich plate with metal foam core struck transversely by a heavy mass with low-velocity, as shown in Fig.1. Large deflection effect is incorporated in analysis by considering the interaction of plastic bending and stretching. The analytical expressions are obtained for the structural deflection, the structural response time and the impact force. The finite element results validate the accuracy of the analytical model and good agreement is achieved, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1 Sketch of a fully clamped sandwich square plate struck by a heavy mass G with an initial low velocity V_0 . (a) Isometric view, and (b) front view.

Fig. 2 Comparisons of the analytical predictions and FE results for the non-dimensional maximum deflections of the sandwich square plate as a function of the non-dimensional impact energy of the striker at (a) P1, and (b) P2.

Keywords: Sandwich plate; Metal foam core; Low-velocity impact; Large deflection; Dynamic plasticity.

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